

UNDERGRADUATES' REACTION TO MEDIA PORTRAYAL OF MUSICAL CELEBRITIES IN NIGERIA: A STUDY OF UNIVERSITY OF UYO, NIGERIA

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Abstract

This study, titled "Undergraduates' Reaction to Media Portrayal of Musical Celebrities in Nigeria: A Study of University of Uyo, Nigeria," aimed to systematically assess how Uniuyo undergraduates respond to media portrayals of musical celebrities in Nigeria. It also examines how musical celebrities are depicted in Nigerian media and the perception of Uniuyo undergraduates regarding media objectivity in portraying these celebrities. The study employs both the modelling theory of mass communication, derived from Albert Bandura's (1977) social learning theory, and Stuart Hall's (1980) Audience Reception Theory as its theoretical frameworks. The population consisted of 27,980 students from the 12 faculties at the University of Uyo, Nigeria. A sample size of 400 respondents was selected using the Taro Yamane formula. A simple random sampling technique was used to choose 2 departments from each of the 12 faculties for the study. Data collection was carried out using questionnaires. The data were analysed using descriptive statistics, including frequencies and simple percentages. The findings revealed that the majority of Uniuyo undergraduates frequently watch or listen to media content featuring musical celebrities, with 98% affirming this. The study also found that 85% of respondents held a negative perception about media objectivity in its portrayal of musical celebrities in Nigeria. Based on these results, it is recommended that media regulators ensure that producers do not allow commercial interests of advertisers to influence content creation, in order to prevent the exploitation of young minds.

Keywords: *Media, Reaction, Media Portrayal, Musical celebrities, Perception*

Introduction

Musical celebrities in Nigeria have continued to enjoy an increasing popularity among the youth. Music has been a form of communication, and William Shakespeare in his play “Twelfth Night” said: “If music is the food of the soul, give me excess of it”. Music permeates every aspect of human existence, ranging from birthdays and wedding ceremonies to funeral events. Music is used to add colour to social gatherings; hence, it is a medium for communication and expression of social reality and culture.

Uzuegbunam (2017) posits that interest in the famous seems to be a human phenomenon that goes as far back as recorded history. Humans often appear captivated by those they see as glamorous. In Ancient Greece and Rome, people created their gods as very human-like beings, complete with character flaws. In the contemporary world, this phenomenon is being facilitated by the media. Today, young people are exposed to an immense range of influential figures through television and radio, popular culture, print media and the internet. This development has led scholars to interrogate how this affects young people and broaden the scope of celebrity studies. Carlin (2004) recounts that celebrities are fascinating because they live in a parallel universe—one that looks and feels just like ours yet is light-years beyond our reach. Celebrities, as Carlin pronounced, are without ordinary folks, just like us, but such thinking seems to be more logical than is the case in real life. This is so because with the rise in popular culture at the turn of the century, celebrities have assumed a god-like status in society. They have become objects of fascination and wonder. They are idolised and looked up to by society. Human beings have an instinct to look to someone for reflection, affirmation and authority, whether as a hero, mentor, protector or higher power (Uzuegbunam, 2017).

Mell (2009) bemoans our fascination with celebrity culture and some of its ugly consequences by positing that in our culture, celebrity news often takes the headlines about world events. We build them up as modern gods and tear them down when they show us they are all too human. They make an easy object of obsession, as celebrities are ubiquitous. And the paparazzi have helped this craze by blurring the line between private citizens and public persons. When princess Diana died, it was in high speed, a gateway to escape reporters/stalkers. French courts ruled that photographers were not responsible for her death, but it clearly drives home the point: our obsession with the rich and famous has a cost on us, and on them.

The youths are perhaps the most affected by the famous culture, especially students of higher institutions of learning, who are not spared either, since most of them are still in that contemplative age, the age of uncertainty, negotiating future goals and aspirations. It has been argued that the mass media have the singular potential to set agendas for society in which they are embedded. They may not tell us what to think, but they have become successful in telling and suggesting to us what to think about. In the same vein, the media have been known to confer status on personalities and place due or undue importance on them.

In Nigeria, and indeed in parts of Africa, the phenomenon of celebrity culture, which, from all indications, is a Western cultural experience, is rapidly permeating the mainstream cultural system of these societies (Uzuegbu, 2015). At the turn of the century, Nigerian media had produced a great medium of celebrities arising from the multiplicity of popular media. These celebrities have also had their lifestyles hyped and glamorised in the media, resulting in a recent explosion of attention given to these media figures. Ndlela (2006) asserts that in

Africa, youth live and constitute their identities in a world that is increasingly shaped by the global communication networks and global consumption patterns flowing through the mass media.

The media, a product of technological advancement in communication, can be described as a force that has not only come into existence for a lifetime but has to stay for an indefinite period (Nzekwe, Ngonso & Oyewole, 2020). The media has become a force that most people of all ages and walks of life are accessible to and become exposed to its content, thereby having a sense of attachment to it. This implies that platforms are carriers of information to the public at large and have become social influencers. The media today, can have effects on the audience because of the craze to get and consume more information from the media and the media has been driven by this craze to create more and more media platforms as assisted by the technology developers who have come up with blogs (gossip blogs), political blogs, fashion blogs, general purpose blogs and so on) instant messaging, i-report coners etc. Nzekwe et al (2020) posit that the insatiable need for media products and the appeal it has to the audience due to the variety of programmes on the media (including movies, music, news, etc) targeting various categories of the media audience, the mass media audience becomes “media-cannibals”.

According to Anderson, Berkovitz, Donnerstein, Huesmann, Johnson, Linz, Malamuth and Wartella (2003), continuous use of the media and exposure to its generated programmes affect the audience as they affect behaviour through priming cognitions and eliciting effects on a short-term basis. A long-term exposure to the media affects “beliefs, perceptions, behavioural scripts and affective traits, bringing about lasting personality changes” (Huesmann & Kirwit, 2007). Before the advancement in technology, which came with modern music, traditional music was often used by singers to portray their cultural identities. Music can also be used to fight social ills in society (Onyegiri, 2018). Olatunji (2007) identifies the stimulating or motivating role whereby the music serves as a stimulant or motivator, moving the people into action against oppressive and repressive forces in society. There is also the propaganda role played by music that the exponents criticise governments, systems and society to force them to change anti-societal programmes.

Beyond being a voice for the voiceless, music plays an essential role in cultural promotion and preservation. Adegaju (2009) posits that artists can be seen as “town criers” who satirise social foibles to make human society and living worthwhile, which is an important cultural element of developing countries that face extreme social and economic hardship.

O'Rorke (2006) posits that the mass media play a central role in influencing human behaviour through symbolic models presented in media content. Some scholars and social commentators have decried the general trend towards the trivialization of news. They also argue that the current obsession with celebrity news is emblematic. We find young people, including the students, being exposed, for better or for worse, to an immense range of influential figures through radio and television, popular culture, print media and the internet (Giles & Malby, 2003 as cited in Uzuegbunam, 2017). This is possible because we live in a celebrity-obsessed world or culture, which is an obvious and stressed observation.

The situation is now compounded by the global youth culture, which is an offshoot of the rising popular culture like music, dance, arts, theatre, movies and the internet, as promoted by the western media conglomerates. The submission above paints a vivid picture

of the media portrayal of celebrities in Nigeria and the perception of the youths of today, especially the undergraduates in our universities. In line with the submission, this study examines the reaction of Uniuyo undergraduates to media portrayals of musical celebrities in Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

Humans are naturally captivated by those they perceive as glamorous. Having an interest in celebrities seems to be a human event that dates back to recorded history. Celebrity is an encompassing word or term defining a person widely recognised due to the degree of public and media attention the person commands and the person they exhibit or represent. It has been argued that media reality is a power that defines which set of individuals would bask in the spotlight of the media. The media messages can blur, bend and blend the opinion-making process of the audience, and the perception of reality of the audience is said to be greatly affected by the media. The celebrities are constructed in the minds of the media audience. These celebrities exert certain influence on the audience based on media portrayals. They also tend to win the support of the audience for what they stand for. However, some scholars argue that media messages are not sufficient to promote personalities beyond what individual audience members know about the celebrities.

Musical celebrities can trigger powerful emotions, and often in conjunction with a memory, but sometimes not, because music is not a one-size-fits-all experience. We must not lose sight of the fact that entertainment drives musicals and society today, as one of the key elements of entertainment is musicals. When these celebrities are promoted in the media, and as a result of what some scholars call “15 minutes of fame”, they instantly assume a famous status. They become regular faces on television, front cover of glossy magazines, on the internet, and are used for advertisement of all types and on billboards. In the end, these images are likely to have some reactions from media users, including university undergraduates. It is in the light of these views that this study on “Undergraduates' reaction to media portrayal of musical celebrities in Nigeria: a study of University of Uyo, Nigeria” is anchored and the result of which certainly contributes to the existing body of knowledge.

Objectives of the Study

The objectives of the study were to:

- (i) Determine how often Uniuyo undergraduates listen to or watch musical celebrities in the media.
- (ii) Find out Uniuyo undergraduates' reaction to media portrayal of musical celebrities.
- (iii) Find out Uniuyo undergraduates' perception of media objectivity in its portrayal of musical celebrities.

Review of Related Literature

The Media

The media, a product of technological advancement in communication, can be described as a force that has not only come into existence for a lifetime but has become here to stay for an indefinite period. It is a force accessible to most people of all ages and walks of life, exposing them to its contents, thereby fostering a sense of attachment. Nzekwe, Ngonso, and Oyewole (2017) observed that the insatiable need for media products and their appeal—due to the variety of programmes (including music and movies, etc.) targeting different audience categories—turns the mass media audience into “media-cannibals.” This term describes the

process by which media consumers (such as Uniuyo undergraduates) shift from consuming media messages about musical celebrities sparingly to consuming them extensively, surplus, and in some cases, addictively. Uzuebumam (2017) asserts that one way young people express their youthfulness today is through new technologies and the media. They seek to define themselves through their attire, unique jargon, experiences, hairstyles, group affiliations, and the images from media sources (such as soft-sell magazines, popular music, movies, talk shows, celebrity interviews, and technological advancements, along with the appeals they carry). These often provide the external basis for young people to gauge their thoughts, dreams, opinions, preferences, and associations. The reactions of young people to media portrayals of musical celebrities vary widely. Today, young people are, for better or worse, exposed to an immense range of influential figures through television, radio, popular culture, print media, and the internet. Ndlela (2006), writing about Zimbabwean youth and their negotiations with identity formation, notes that in recent years, the global popular celebrity culture has become a contested space for the negotiation of identities in African cities. He also observed that new technologies and globalisation are influencing every aspect of social life in cities across Africa, directly or indirectly.

Media platforms are carriers of information to the public at large and have become social influencers. The functions of informing, educating, persuading and ofcourse entertaining which the media perform, are core components that appeal to human society and therefore making media messages of great importance to members of the public.

The media has contributed to shaping the audience's thought process and perception towards products, events, and personalities portrayed on the media, which also influences the decisions of the audience (Uniuyo undergraduates) after being exposed to the media depiction of musical celebrities. Changes induced by the media in its audience can be said to extend to the psychographic level, as the mass media hold a significant influence and impact on the perception of the audience exposed to its content, while also involving some level of psychological thinking.

The new media technology, according to Ezekwe et al (2020) is a term describing the revolution that is and will continue to affect the information and communication technology, but today refers to communication and information software that are internet based which include social networking sites such as facebook and Twitter now known as x, bogs, websites etc. Blogs have become a common trend amidst media audience because of its ease of access both by the blogger and the audience. A blog started off as a web log (online diary) but has now become a great source for news, even celebrity news. There has been insatiable need for media products today and the appeal it has to the audience because of the variety of porgammes on the media.

Asemah (2011) described the new media as term that refers to “digital interactive media” which was popularized in the twentieth century indicating the amalgamation of traditional media such as films, images, music, spoken and written words, with the interactive power of computer and communications technology, computer-enabled consumer devices and most importantly the internet”.

Celebrity is perceived as a profession beyond the gasps of ordinary members of the society as the actors of a certain rank, performers who have reached the top rung of an insular profession and regarded as celebrities (Newbury, 2000). Gabler (2007) also said celebrity in the form of an action relating to human entertainment “as” a person who by the very process of living, provides entertainment for the audience. Some celebrities are most time famous for

an infamous act like challenging societal values and being controversial in nature. For example, Kimkardashian, Vanua White, and Nicole Richie. We have in Nigeria, Toke Makinwa, Bob Rosky and so on.

Media Portrayal

The perception of individuals about celebrities is moulded by the media because of its large reach mostly in an age of new media technology where the media is at one's fingertips making it impossible to avoid contact with the media in this virtual world. As a result of this nature of the media, the media now can make or mar a celebrity. Boorstin (1962) stated that modern celebrity is marked by media manipulations that “hoodwinks the public”. This means that media has an excessive amount of power to establish, maintain, and destroy celebrity status. Palmer (2008) explains that the media conveys what and who the audience should think about and what to feel about the situations and light celebrities are presented in relation to societal norms of that time in a particular society.

Musical Celebrities

Before the advancement in technology which came with modern music, traditional music was often used by singers to portray their cultural identities. Music can also be used to fight social ills in the society. Olatunji (2007) identifies the stimulating or motivating role whereby the music serves as, a stimulant or motivator, moving people into action against oppressive and repressive forces in society. Beyond being a voice for the voiceless, music plays a very essential role in cultural promotion and preservation. Adegoju (2009) posts that musical artistes can be seen as “town criers” who satirize social foibles in order to make human society and living worthwhile which is an important cultural element of developing countries that face extreme social and economic hardship. Musical celebrities are those famous and glamorous musical artistes as facilitated by the media.

They perform such functions as status-conferral and agenda-setting through the power of music. Musical celebrities have the power to set agenda on issues and confer status on personalities in societies in which they are found. Today, young people are exposed, to an immense range of influential celebrities through television and radio, popular culture, print media and internet which has made scholars to go into interrogation of how this has affected young people and broaden the scope of celebrity study (Uzuegbunam, 2017).

Celebrity and the Audience

Obviously, the process of commodification and personalization of celebrities by the media considers the interest and the attention of the audience as very important, and that is why the media adapts to the condition of “Attention Economy” as rightly observed by Davenport & Beck, (2001). Attention Economy as a principle describes the process of devising new strategies that would grasp audience attention, which is what led to the regarding of celebrities as vehicle of attention to increase the number of viewers and readers Heumueller & Deschbacher, 2010).

Redmond & Holmes (2007) observe that for the media to continually benefit from the celebrity enterprise the needful must be done which is the continuous consumption and reception of stories about celebrity by the audience. To further understand the importance of the audience to the making of a celebrity and sustaining celebrity status, Gabler, cited in Ozekwe et al (2020) described celebrities as “people who take the national stage, do their act

and leave and invited to return only when they have something new to perform.

This means that without support from the public and an ability to intrigue the audience, a celebrity would not be a celebrity (Gregory, 2008). Wippersberg (2007) emphasizes that for celebrity remains a celebrity is dependent on the audience embracing and perceiving such individual or group of individuals as a celebrity. This means that even if the media introduces a person as a potential celebrity, the person cannot become a celebrity without consent from the audience, that is, a celebrity without a fan base on interested audience is not a celebrity (Seifert, 2010). Maintaining the position of celebrity is a not child's play because it is not so easy to continually maintain the attention of audience as it is fickle in nature. The perception of individuals about celebrities is moulded by the media because of its large reach most especially in an age of new media technology where the media is at one's fingertips making it impossible to avoid contact with the media in this virtual world. As a result of this nature of media, the media can make or mar a celebrity. This further implies that the media has an excessive amount of power to establish, maintain, and destroy celebrity status. The media may choose to downplay certain celebrities or facts of their existence while choosing to sensationalize others (Gregory, 2008).

Recently, with the diversification of media business interest as well as the development of convergent new media technologies, celebrity, are traded like commodities across media platforms and global markets. Foreign television channels and satellite broadcasts of foreign media, through a diffusion process, filter the lifestyles mediated in these channels in African societies in general and Nigeria in particular. As majority of Nigerian youths use mobile phones that are imbued with internet facilities (Utzuegbunam, 2015), they enjoy a different and more ubiquitous kind of access.

Youths' Perception of Musical Celebrities and Nigerian Culture

Though music basically entertains people, the manner of the entertainment speaks volume of the culture of the people. Music is the entrainment aspects of culture. It acts as a sort of therapy for both the body and the soul. In some societies and countries music is as important as food. The representation of the Nigerian culture by Nigerian musical celebrities have been a source of worry with some people arguing that Nigerian musicians are not properly representing Nigerian culture. According to Dympna (2018), this argument has been strengthened by the perceived moral decadence among Nigerian youths. The situation has been compounded with the emergence of smartphones and mobile technologies which make it possible for people to listen and even watch musical videos, wherever they may be.

Celebrity studies is a new and emerging area in Nigeria and for this reason most studies conducted in this area are carried out by scholars in the western world. Johanson (2015) as in Nzekwe et al (2020) carries out a research on celebrity culture and audiences: a Swedish case study and examined how media consumers of different age, gender and socio-economic backgrounds in Stockholm relate to and talk about celebrities and celebrity media.

Based on 16 small focus groups with 17 year olds and 45-55 years old, with male and female participants from working class as well as academic backgrounds, she investigated a range of responses to celebrity content in connection with overall media developments in Sweden. The purpose of the study was to gain insights into what the contemporary culture emphasis on celebrity can mean on an audience level within a particular context. Omenugha et al., (2016) in their study on celebrity culture, media and the Nigerian youth: negotiating cultural identities in a globalized world, was to examine in the context of Nigeria, whether celebrity culture is being appropriated by Nigerian youths through their various experiences

of the media. A further aim was to establish whether such appropriation has any influence on their social behaviours and attitudes. Drawing the respondents from undergraduates at two universities in Nigeria, and employing qualitative and quantitative methodologies, the study found that indications are rise of western celebrity culture being perpetuated by both mainstream and alternative media, and that there appears to be an emerging and empowering hybridization of African and Western cultures, as the Nigerian youths negotiate their cultural identities.

Wright & Craske (2015), investigated music's influence on risky sexual behaviours. The researchers examined the relationship between sexual context in music lyrics and music videos and the sexual behaviour of Caucasian, African American and Hispanic emerging adults from a cultivation framework by assessing 715 male and female students. The results from hierarchical regression analysis indicated that sexual lyrical content in music videos, along with participant gender race/ethnicity, are correlated with the dating and sexual behaviours of participants. Another study by Uzuegbunam (2017), which sought to find out whether youths are exposed to media contents that glamorize and glorify the lifestyles of celebrities-local or international. The data indicated that the respondents were aware of various media of communication that glamorize the lifestyles of celebrities in Nigeria, while barely 15.2% were not familiar with such media.

In the study, 71 percent agreed that they are familiar with the details of the lives of foreign celebrities, while 4.8 of them at 28.9% were not. The youth surveyed were exposed to media that glamorize local as well as foreign celebrities. This fact was further buttressed by their wide knowledge of celebrities from other parts of the world from different categories of the culture industry. Another aspect of the study sought to find out whether the lifestyles of celebrities as portrayed by the media have any impact on the attitudes and behaviours of youth. Data showed that appropriately 79% of the respondents were captivated by the lifestyles of popular celebrities. For 46.2%, their degree of this captivation was strong, 64.5 said they are influenced by the appearance or lifestyle of any popular celebrity and 43.4% admitted that the celebrities affect the way they think about sex, relationships and marriage. Furthermore, approximately 99% think celebrities in general have an influence on the attitude and behaviour of Nigerian youth generally. The previous study aligns with the present study in terms of scope and focus of the study. The present study took a radical departure from the previous study in the area of theoretical application and area of research and that is the gap that this present study intends to fill.

In their study, Boon & Lomore (2001) cited in Nzekwe et al (2020) explained in the research entitled "Amirer-celebrity relationship among youth adults explaining perception of celebrity influence on identity which invested young adults' judgements regarding the degree to which relationships with celebrity idols influenced their sense of identity and feelings of self-worth. In the study, participants (N=75) were recruited from larger sample (N = 213) of young adults whose responses to a brief survey instrument indicated that they were moderately too strongly attracted to media figures they identified as idol in their lives. The study considered the characteristics of the sample of idol participants reported as well as descriptive data concerning the degree to which participants perceived these idols as influential in shaping their sense of identity and feelings of self-worth. The previous study was a paper discussion with no theoretical anchorage but using a brief survey instrument. The present study is different from the previous study in terms of the sample size, theoretical application and the scope of the research.

Ezuegbuam, (2017) in his study, it sought to find out whether the lifestyles of celebrities as portrayed by the any impact or the activities and behaviours of youth. Data showed that approximately 79% of the respondents were captivated by the lifestyle of popular celebrities. For 46.2% their degree of this captivation was strong. 64.5% said they are influenced by the appearance or lifestyle of any popular celebrity, and 43.4% admitted that the celebrities affect the way they think about sex, relationship and marriage.

Furthermore, approximately 99% think celebrities in general have influence on the attitude and behaviour of the Nigerian youth. It was a qualitative data that lend to furnish further insight into the phenomenon. The respondents' responses suggested that they are captivated by these celebrities-strongly and partially, and they are affected by their lifestyle/appearance in many ways. The present study aligns with this study but with a radical departure inters of area of study and theory application.

Theoretical Framework

Audience Reception Theory

This theory was propounded by Stuart Hall in 1980. According to Julie Martin (2007) defined the theory as the “Encoding-Decoding” means of communication where the media encodes a message to suit a particular context and the audience decode the message based on their own ideologies. The study describes the audience as being active rather than passive when taking in media texts, information and messages. This explains the fact that one message can be understood from several points of view. Stuart Hall outlined three positions audience can take to decode media messages. They are dominant or preferred position, oppositional and negotiated position.

Dominant or preferred position allows for little misunderstanding or miscommunication as the sender and receiver are classified under the same cultural bases, assumptions and rules, hence, the way the sender package a message is the way the receiver would interpret the message. Oppositional position describes when audience decode messages in the way of the encoder's intent, but disagree and create their own meaning from the message based on their beliefs. It happens when controversial themes are raised in the message and the encoder and decoder have different social values and culture bias. Negotiated position of the audience explains the compromise of the audience in the process of decoding a message in the media. The audience here understands the media message but accepts part of the media's view in addition to their own view. Some factors that also determine the position audience take while decoding a message (about musical celebrities) include life experience, mood at the time of viewing, age, culture, beliefs, gender etc.

In the case of this study on Uniuyo undergraduates' reaction to media portrayal of musical celebrities in Nigeria, it implies that media which act as the encoder of message about musical celebrities, could portray these celebrities either positively or negatively but because Uniuyo undergraduates are seen as active and not passive users, the perception or reaction they tend to have about musical celebrities in Nigeria, is a result of the interpretation they have attached to the message the media reported about musical celebrities and then decide if they would position themselves as dominant, oppositional or negotiated audience.

The Modelling Theory of Mass Communication

This theoretical framework underpins this study on reaction of Uniuyo undergraduates to media portrayal of musical celebrities in Nigeria. The theory was a spin-off

from Albert Bandura (1977's) social learning theory which reveals that “learning would be exceedingly labourious, not to mention hazardous, if people had to rely solely on the effects of their own actions to inform them what to do.

Fortunately, most human behaviour is learned observationally through modelling from observing others, one forms an idea of how new behaviours are performed, and on later occasions this coded information serves as a guide for action”. Modelling theory has since become a theory scholars of communication use to explain long-term influences of mass communications this means that, it can help in explaining why minor changes take place among individuals, eventually to accumulate in major changes in society (Defleaur & Dennis, 1998).

This theory as the fundamental theory for this study will help to shed light on the growing culture that appeal to the young people videos, the internet, and other popular and alternative media, the media create images of celebrity especially musical celebrities in Nigeria and will also address the issues of the reaction of Uniuyo undergraduates to media portrayal of musical celebrities in Nigeria as it affects the lifestyle and attitudes of Uniuyo undergraduates. The media are no doubt selective in their representation of the construct images and behaviours for different groups within the society. They present many depictions of people acting out patterns of behaviour in various ways. Indeed, the media have the power through selection and reinforcement to give us very influential portrayals of a whole range of groups, situations and ideas. Such groups can be media characters or celebrities. Through television, movies, magazines, music videos, the internet, and other popular and alternative media, the media create images that appeal to the young people and this has the ability to control the variety of material these young people incorporate into their lives. This theory therefore comes in handy as an appropriate assumption that situate this interplay between the reaction of Uniuyo undergraduates and media portrayal of musical celebrities in Nigeria.

Methodology

This study employs the survey research design for the purpose of obtaining data to enable the researcher answer research questions. The essence of the survey research design is to observe the sample subjects without any attempt to manipulate or control them and to determine the interrelatedness between reaction of Uniuyo undergraduates and media portrayal of musical celebrities in Nigeria. The survey research design also interprets, synthesizes; and integrates data and points to relationships and application. The major characteristic of all survey research designs is lack of control, but focuses on people's opinions, attitudes, behaviour and motivation. Babie (2008) opines that it is the best method available to the social researcher who is interested in collecting original data for describing a population too large to observe directly. The justification for the choice of survey research design is that apart from being a necessary part of research proposal and research report, survey research design can be used as a guide for data collection. The focus of the study was on Uniuyo undergraduates both male and female students with a population of 127,980 from the 12 faculties of the university. 400 sample size was drawn using Taro Yamane formula.

Result

In analysing data for the study the researcher used descriptive statistics which include simple percentages and frequencies.

Table 1: Frequency of watching musical celebrities on media

Frequency	Number	Percentage (%)
Very often	144	41
Often	200	57
Undecided	6	2
Total	350	100

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Here, information was sought on how often the respondents watch musical celebrities on media. As indicated in table 1, the majority of respondents (344 or 98%) indicated that they watched musical celebrities on media very often and often times.

Table 2: Uniuyo undergraduates' reaction to media portrayal of musical celebrities

Responses	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Negative Reaction	199	57
Positive Reaction	143	41
Undecided	8	2
Total	350	100

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Table 2 shows that majority of Uniuyo undergraduates (57%) have a negative reaction to media portrayal of musical celebrities.

Table 3: Uniuyo undergraduates' perception of media objectivity in its portrayal of musical celebrities

Responses	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Negative Reaction	199	57
Positive Reaction	143	41
Undecided	8	2
Total	350	100

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Table 3 indicates that 85% of the respondents have a negative perception of media objectivity in its portrayal of musical celebrities.

Discussion of Major Findings

Findings of the study show that majority of the respondents listen to or watch musical celebrities on media. This is further supported with data on table two. It was gathered that 57% of the respondents often times listen to or watch musical celebrities on media. Again 41% of the respondents listen to or watch musical celebrities on media very often. This finding consolidates existing literature (Devadas & Ravi, 2013) in their study “on cultural impact of television on urban youth – An empirical study” where 38% of the respondents reported that they watch television a minimum of one to a maximum of two hours in a day while 11% of the respondents spend not less than three hours in day watching television. The

findings affirm the Audience Reception Theory of Stuart Hall which describes the audience as being active rather than passive when taking in media information, text and message. According to Uzuegbunan (2012) human being have a natural instinct to look to someone for reflection, affirmation and authority, whether as a hero, mentor, protector or higher power. The data also affirm the tenets of the modelling theory of mass communication as the fundamental theory that help to shed light on the growing culture that appeal to the young people which includes videos, internet and other popular and alternative media that creates images of celebrity.

Findings show that majority of Uniuyo undergraduates have a negative reaction to media portrayal of musical celebrities. This finding is further supported with data on table 3 while shows that 57% of the respondents have a negative reaction to media portrayal of musical celebrities, which 41% of the respondents have a positive reaction to media portrayal of media portrayal of musical celebrities. This finding is a confirmation of existing literature (Palmer, 2008) who explains that the media conveys what and who the audience should think about and what to feel about the situations and light celebrities are presented in relation to societal norms of that time in a particular society. According to Boorstin (1962) modern celebrity is marked by media manipulations that hoodwinks the public. The finding affirms Uzuegbunan (2017) who asserts that one of the ways in which young people express their youthfulness in the present generation is through new technologies and media as they are thought what the wear, their peculiar jagon, experiences, hair styles and group associations.

Findings of the study show that majority of the respondents have a negative perception to media objectivity in its portrayal of musical celebrities. The finding further confirms the data on table four which shows that 85% of the respondents have a negative perception to media objectivity in its portrayal of musical celebrities, while only 9% of the respondents say that they have positive perception to media objectivity of its portrayal of musical celebrities. This finding consolidates existing literature (Gregory, 2008) who asserts that celebrities can be replaced easily in the eyes of the audience because if the celebrity has nothing to offer, the audience might lose interest in such individuals.

Conclusion

Based on the above findings, it was concluded that it is evident from the study that Uniuyo undergraduates are ardent watchers of media portrayal of musical celebrities in Nigeria as they were found to watch media portrayal of musical celebrities very often. The media portrayal of musical celebrities has serious influence on the respondents who are audience members as they desire to be stars like them after watching the celebrities on media platforms.

It is the conclusion of the study that Uniuyo undergraduates have a negative reaction to media portrayal of musical celebrities. The perception of media of objectivity in its coverages by Uniuyo undergraduates is overwhelmingly a negative perception. The study affirms the promotion of celebrity culture by the media. This promotion of media culture by the media has made the society that we live in a celebrity-obsessed world.

The study identifies some areas of deficiencies in media portrayal of musical celebrities. These areas of deficiencies include degrading sexual content, lack of musical therapeutic effect content and exploitative contents of the media portrayal of musical celebrities.

Recommendations

Given the findings and conclusions reached, the following recommendations were put forward.

- (i) Since media portrayal of musical celebrities in Nigeria are very often watched by the undergraduates, regulators of media houses must ensure that producers do not allow the commercial interest of advertisers to influence what they produce or put as content with a view to avoiding exploitation of young minds.
- (ii) As media portrayal of musical celebrities have serious influences on audience members as they desire to be stars like the people they watch, audience members must observe caution while watching media portrayal of musical celebrities because not all that happen in the media are real.
- (iii) The Nigerian film and video censorship board should step up efforts in making sure that music content released into the Nigerian market do not corrupt the Nigerian culture by making the society a celebrity-obsessed society
- (iv) The Nigerian musical artiste should refrain from producing music videos that do not promote the culture and music contents that corrupt public morals.

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